

HUMANITARIAN CRISES AS CATALYSTS FOR MULTI-POLARITY: THE CASE OF AFGHAN REFUGEES IN IRAN AND PAKISTAN

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Abstract

This era has been marked by a readjustment of global power and how humanitarian crises have gained importance as catalysts in the development of a multi-polar world order. This paper is dedicated to the case of Afghan refugees in Iran and Pakistan: how their plight draws not only attention to crucial humanitarian issues but also exercises impact on diplomatic relations and international cooperation among states. This paper expound on how the point of contacts, like humanitarian needs and geopolitics convergence work in the Afghan refugee crisis. Further how this critical juncture leadsto understand multi-polarity complexities of present era. Afghan refugee inflow into Iran and Pakistan drastically effects regional stability, particularly during this post-Afghanistan's second fall and post-American-withdrawal period of the United States in 2021. This paper utilizes the qualitative approach to study the aspects of refugee demographics and economic impacts in a complementary manner with the qualitative data for all the stake holders, which include the policymakers, NGOs and the refugees themselves. The study has resulted to show that the Afghan refugee crisis has forced Iran and Pakistan to rethink their foreign policy and has prompted a more cooperative regional dialogue. In addition to that, the paper elucidates that the responses of Iran and Pakistan to Afghan refugees exemplify the overall trends of international relations. This research demonstrates how humanitarian crises operate as a driver of change in international relations while using the examples of both nations which have used their host country for Afghan refugees for political gains in the end. The presence of Afghan refugees in Iran and Pakistan shows that crises like this might make states shift in regards to adjusting, cooperating and making new alliances in a multi polar world. The exploration of these dynamics enhances our knowledge of the complexities of the present geopolitics and humanitarian crises that are transforming the manner in which norms and practices of an unstable and cooperative system evolve.

INTRODUCTION

With respect to international relations, there is a change in the projection of global power in favor of

multi-polarity. Powers that do not belong to the West are rising and changing the traditional

geopolitical order. The humanitarian crises, among other things, have emerged as the new issue in this contemporary context that not only affect the policies of the countries concerned, but also the diplomatic dynamics of balance of power. These crises reveal the intermingled notions of state sovereignty, national security, and human rights and how they serve as crucial intersections in global diplomacy and politics (Adamson, 2019). The Afghan Refugee crisis is one of the best instances of how humanitarianism collides with the realpolitik of neighboring countries like Iran and Pakistan who continue to suffer the consequences of the refugee burden (Bohnet, 2024).

Following the fall of the Afghan government in 2021, and the rapid rise of the Taliban regime, millions of refugees fled to neighboring countries, primarily Iran and Pakistan (Javaid F. S., 2024). This drastic increase in the region's population has compounded the issues of border control and social integration, straining the economies and infrastructure of the region (Thomas, 2020). What used to be a simple case of humanitarian aid has now transformed into a much more pressing concern for regional politics and an aspect of the new global great game (Erfan, 2021). This paper addresses the nexus of humanitarian need and geopolitics and analyzes the impact of Afghani refugees in Iran and Pakistan on the foreign policies of the region.

It affects the larger trend of global multi-polarity in that states modify their foreign policy and alliances because of the humanitarian challenges posed by the refugee crisis. These are qualitative, from the perspective of policymakers and NGOs and the refugees themselves, but also secondary demographic and economic impact data. The findings argue that not just Iran but Pakistan too has begun to reconsider their foreign policies in light of this Afghan refugee crisis, resulting in greater cooperative regional dialogue. Thus, it expands on how the humanitarian crises of the Afghan refugees indeed drive changes in international relations as states develop new alliances and engage in cooperative behavior in an increasingly fragmented world. With the analysis of these aspects, this paper adds to how the humanitarian crises have affected the diplomacy and geopolitical relations of states in a multi-polar world (Christensen, 2011).

Literature Review

For some years now, humanitarian crises have become a vital part of international relations. Even if such crises are perceived as negative disruptions, their existence on a global and regional scale geopolitics can be important, and even serve as a tool for foreign policy. Paying attention to the theories of authors like Betts (2009), it is clear that host countries see refugees as a burden because of the consumption of resources, existing infrastructure, and security. As mentioned in Betts, "refugee crises pose short-term challenges, but they also reflect a deeper tension between humanitarian imperatives and national interests (Betts, 2009)." Nevertheless, there are those who, like Cohen (2013), argue that refugee crises can be opportunistic, especially from the perspective of state soft powers and their political bargaining. As stated by Cohen, "Refugees can be seen as a tool of state policy, used to influence and shape both bilateral and multilateral relations" (Cohen, 2013). Weng (2021) supports this view, adding that under some circumstances refugee populations behave as a type of asymmetric power, thus enabling weaker states to challenge stronger ones and take control of the narrative associated with the influx of refugees and humanitarian issues (Weng, 2021).

An examination done by Koser (2016) and Van Hear (2009) provides an insight into the long-term consequences of Afghan refugee movements, particularly in terms of its impacts on the area's stability. Some scholars argue that while refugees tend to destabilize regions in the short term, they also have the potential, over the long term, to reshape the geopolitical dynamics of a particular area as the neighboring states become proactive in attending to the influx of displaced peoples from powerful countries. For instance, Koser has put forward the argument which suggests that foreign policy and diplomacy by pro-refugee bordering countries, such as Pakistan and Iran, will be responsive to the changing patterns of refugee movement and resettlement. Thus, there can be a regional balance of power (Koser, 2018). In a very similar manner to most other authors, Van Hear (2009) goes on to articulate how Afghan refugees' protracted situation places tremendous socio-

economic burdens as well as security and even political tension on the countries that host them (Van Hear, 2009).

Van Hear contends that while the refugee question may create internal conflicts within host states, it is also an issue that these countries can use to further their agenda in influencing international policy through the UNHCR, obtaining international assistance (Van Hear 2009). As reported by UNHCR (2023), the problem of refugees has triggered regional discussions about sharing the burden, placing both Iran and Pakistan at the head of the table for these talks (Garnier, 2023).

Elmi (2023) and Lamey (2021) have also analyzed how countries use the refugee problem to enhance their international relations with international bodies, especially when dealing with regions with high refugee concentration. Elmi seeks to elaborate on how the Afghan refugee crisis has become a political endeavor for countries like Iran and Pakistan to garner global assistance while funneling in huge numbers of refugees (Elmi, 2023). This is also evident in the Pakistan case as it works with the UN and other international bodies trying to get money and other resources to manage the influx of refugees (Khan, 2021). Lamey (2021) goes a step ahead of this and explains the contribution of international NGOs in refugee diplomacy. He maintains that the impact of hosting refugees is felt in bilateral relations the same way it is on the global scene. As Lamey suggests, managing the flow of refugees can give governments leverage in international negotiations in regard to human rights and security issues where most nations have opposing views (Lamey, 2021).

While a significant amount of literature on the issue of refugee movements focuses on the humanitarian and security aspects of the host states, comparatively less attention has been paid to the role refugees can play in changing power geopolitically. However, the relations between Iran, Pakistan, and Afghanistan offer a great case to explore this intersection (Javaid, 2024). The current Afghan refugee situation poses vital issues for regional and global order particularly regarding how Iran and Pakistan will respond to these people. For instance, Iran uses the host country status in a manner that seeks to project itself as a major regional player in geopolitics and as the

foremost stakeholder in post Taliban Afghanistan (Akbarzadeh, 2023). At the same time, Pakistan is engaging with international bodies in order to get aid for its refugees (Miller, 2022). This interrelatedness suggests that refugee situations have the potential to change the diplomacy and sovereignty of states in any region and thus alter its balance of power.

Additionally, experts like Mehta (2015) and Patel (2019) contend that Afghan refugees have increased the economic and political integration of South Asia. As Mehta notes, the refugee crisis has also forced Pakistan and Iran to develop cooperative security and infrastructure systems, particularly in the border regions that have been most heavily impacted by the refugee inflow (Mehta, 2021). According to Patel, there is a tendency among countries that host refugees to establish new trade and diplomatic ties to cope with the economic burden the inflow brings, which, in some instances, positively impacts regional integration. These interactions are indicative of how refugee crises can be purposefully manipulated to achieve regional cooperation, even during competing and power-based contexts (Patel, 2022).

This literature offers a simplistic understanding of the humanitarian crises, multipolarity, and refugee diplomacy that sets the stage for the Afghan refugee issue. With the increasing shift towards multipolarity international systems, this is a point in time when refugees have started emerging as significant actors in international relations, and the Afghan refugee crisis illustrates perfectly how states manipulate international relations through such crises. This review serves as a starting point for more thorough consideration of the aspects of humanitarian crises in the context of regional stability and international power by studying the Afghan refugee problem from the diplomatic, security, and economic perspectives. In this manner, the paper seeks to contribute towards greater understanding of how regional and global states attempt to respond to these problems in such a complicated and fast changing political environment.

Research Objectives and Questions

This paper seeks to attain the following objectives:

1. To assess the impact of the Afghan refugee crisis on the foreign policies of Iran and Pakistan.
2. To identify the lessons learned from Pakistan and

Iran's response to Afghan refugee crisis and how humanitarian crises can be the catalyses to a shift toward multi-polarity in changing geopolitical dynamics.

The central research questions are:

1. What lessons can be learned from Pakistan and Iran's responses to the Afghan refugee crisis, and how can humanitarian crises serve as catalysts for multi-polarity, reshaping geopolitical dynamics?
2. How does the Afghan refugee crisis affect the foreign policy and diplomatic relations of Iran and Pakistan?

Methodology

The current research examines secondary data to observe the crisis and its ramification, of the Afghan refugees. Four sources provide a framework to understand the crisis. First, government documents between Iran and Pakistan map refugee strategies, emphasizing developments prior to and after this contrast illustrates how geopolitics play out in domestic and international policy as leaders weigh humanitarian, economic and security concerns. Second, data from UNHCR, IOM and Human Rights Watch offer both quantitative and qualitative crisis insights, and is rooted in human rights and migration narratives. Third, newspapers, columnists map and dynamic international and domestic views, reflecting political discourse, public attitude and changes in diplomacy that entangles Afghanistan, its neighbors and regional powers. Also the scholarly books and journals furnish theoretical premises of the scenarios of geopolitical consequences of a large displacement, for example what refugee flows does to regional stability, cooperation and power relations. By combining this study brings together evidence, policies, and academic data to review the jolt's consequences on relations, regional security, and how humanitarianism and state interests mix together steering international reactions.

Discussion: Humanitarian Need and Geopolitics Convergence

The Afghan refugee crisis has become a pivotal nexus where humanitarian concerns intersect with larger geopolitical interests. As millions of Afghan refugees have fled to neighboring states like Iran and

Pakistan, both countries are at the center of a regional crisis with far-reaching international stakes. This intersection of humanitarian and geopolitical interests is an example of how refugee crises can determine international relations and foreign policy and have implications for diplomatic action and regional stability.

Iran's Humanitarian Responsibilities and Geopolitical Interests

Iran's response to the Afghan refugee crisis has been influenced both by its centuries-old history as a host country and by the more recent pressures of the magnitude of the flow. Iran shares a large border with Afghanistan and has therefore been a principal destination for Afghan refugees fleeing violence and instability. Iran has accepted Afghan refugees for decades, especially since the Soviet invasion of Afghanistan in the 1980s, and past history is a key consideration in Iran's foreign policy and humanitarian engagement today (Nunan, 2022). The huge intake due to the revival of the Taliban in 2021 aggravated pre-existing pressures on Iran's fragile economy and overstretched social infrastructure (Kagan, 2022). Therefore, the crisis of refugees has now become both a humanitarian and geopolitical crisis, particularly in view of Iran's longstanding disputes with the United States and its sophisticated relations within the Middle East, particularly with rival nations such as Saudi Arabia.

Iran has positioned itself politically as a host state to negotiate foreign support and assistance, yet it campaigns for being humanitarian and derives geopolitical influence. Iran, as explained by the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (OLUWATOSIN, 2024), has been clear about its demand for more international burden-sharing, detailing how the outsized burden of taking in millions of refugees burdens its already shaky economy. Iran's response for itself has been to obtain funding and logistical backing from the world outside, but also from the nearby local powers like Russia and China to which Tehran is presently appealing more urgently for allies with which to defy Western pressure (Selenica, 2021). Iran's geopolitical approach is to leverage the location of being the epicenter of the refugee crisis to emerge more advantageously in international negotiations,

especially when it is negotiating matters like nuclear diplomacy and regional security (Javaid F. D., 2022). In addition, Iran's human rights commitments are generally cast in terms of its general need to offer regional stability. The presence of Afghan refugees is perceived as stabilizing to the extent that it has enabled Iran to exert influence on the affairs of Afghanistan, particularly by contributing to Afghan Shiite militias and participating in the politics of the Middle East (Karataş, 2021).

However, the role also complicates Iran's relationship with Western countries, since the West has replied to Iran on human rights grounds, e.g., the way it has treated refugees. Iran's balancing act between humanitarian responsibility and geopolitics shows the nuanced dance between human rights, national interest, and regional balance in contemporary geopolitics.

Pakistan: Strategic Interests and Diplomatic Leverage

Pakistan, too, has humanitarian as well as geopolitical pressures in dealing with Afghan refugees. Pakistan has a long history of many years of taking in Afghan refugees, with large numbers arriving after the Soviet invasion and the subsequent wars. Nevertheless, the current refugee crisis, precipitated by the fall of the Afghan government and the reemergence of the Taliban, poses new challenges to Pakistan (Loft, 2021). The government's response to the refugee crisis is closely tied with its strategic interests in Afghanistan, especially regarding security and regional power.

Pakistan has long viewed Afghanistan as a vital area for advancing its geopolitical interests, such as maintaining influence over the Afghan Taliban and defending its borders from militants. The refugee crisis merely accelerated these dynamics, especially as Pakistan's relationship with India continues to be driven by competition for regional influence and security interests. While Pakistan maintains its support for the Taliban, it is engaged in a delicate balancing act of retaining its interests in the area against the requirement of international aid and assistance to manage the refugee crisis (Fayyaz, 2023). Pakistan's Afghan refugee policy is not just a humanitarian issue but a policy tool in its larger geopolitical objectives. By hosting Afghan refugees,

Pakistan seeks to determine its relevance in regional and international diplomatic politics, as a prime player in South Asian security and as a critical ally to China and the United States (Sharp, 2002). Pakistan's engagement with global powers over the refugee crisis lays bare the evolving nature of diplomatic influence.

While the refugee crisis has generated some international acknowledgment of Pakistan's status as a host country, it has also been leveraged as a bargaining tool in Pakistan's relations with regional and global powers alike. For example, Pakistan has used the refugee crisis to emphasize its strategic location in the context of the wider U.S.-China competition, calling for greater economic and military aid from both parties (Irfan, 2023). In this context, the Cohen (2012) stated that, the refugee crisis becomes a tool for extracting diplomatic and economic gains, showing how humanitarian crises can be used as a tool of "soft power" diplomacy to enable smaller states such as Pakistan to determine the terms of engagement with powerful global actors.

Refugee Crisis as a Geopolitical Lever: Implications for Regional Stability

The reaction of Iran and Pakistan to the Afghan refugee crisis is indicative of the degree to which humanitarian concerns have come to dominate diplomatic relations and geopolitical realignments. In each instance, the refugee crisis itself is not merely a matter of the provision of assistance but a vehicle by which regional power is asserted and these nations are placed within the international system. The use of refugee populations as negotiating levers in international diplomacy is one facet of a broader trend where states both view refugees as the byproducts of war but increasingly as geopolitical tools themselves (Nazari, 2020).

Both countries have tried to garner international legitimacy and support for their handling of the refugee crisis even as they work on their broader political and security interests. The refugee crisis has thus become a priority in the strategic thinking of both countries, which has informed their relations with both Western countries and emerging regional actors such as China and Russia (Yar, 2023). The intersection of human need and political desire in the Afghan refugee crisis underscores the manner in

which governments balance the tension posed by global migration, here highlighting how geostrategic and humanitarian interests are now inextricably linked.

Despite the last decades, there have been readjustments toward a more multi-polar world system on the global balance of power. The rise of non Western powers and regional powers, the rise of sophistication of geopolitical environments all have marked it. The humanitarian crisis has even become one of the main motivators for such a shift due to the crisis overshadowing international politics and foreign policy. The humanitarian crises impinge on regional equanimity and international coalescence between states as they place national security, economic stability, and social integration of states under duress (Vestenskov, 2016).

A very worthwhile case study of a humanitarian crisis putting to the test diplomatic relations and forcing the reorientation of the foreign policy is the case of the Afghan refugee crisis in Pakistan and Iran. Afghan refugees, who fled the homeland amid decades of war and the latest political turmoil in the wake of the U.S. In the last three decades, world power relations have been changing toward a deeper rebalancing into a more multi polar international order. All of which has been dominated by non Western powers, the rise of regional players, as well as the increasing complexity of geopolitical landscapes. Amongst the most significant drivers of this change is that its one of the core places in international relations and diplomacy, humanitarian crisis happening now. In turn, such crises not only have wide ranging implications for regional stability, but also broader state cooperation implications, internationally given the important implications of social coherence, national security and the financial system. A wonderful case study of how diplomatic reorientation and foreign policy has stretch to deal with the Pakistan and Iran’s Afghan refugee crisis. Sufferings of Afghan refugees who had to leave their

homeland by consequence of war lasting decades, and also at the present political upheaval and the United States military withdrawal from Afghanistan in 2021, have implications for the countries where they are hosted. The essay brings forward a connection to the geopolitical interests and multiple polarity of the war torn world of today with reference to the Afghan refugee crisis in Iran and Pakistan. Host nations carry a strong geopolitical impact for the Afghanistan troop pullout in 2021. Geopolitically, this essay looks at the Afghan Refugee crisis in Pakistan and Iran in order to show the multi polarity of today (Tellis 2010).

The Afghan Refugee Crisis: Context and Humanitarian Challenges

The Afghan refugee crisis is not a new phenomenon, with millions of Afghans fleeing their country over the past four decades due to various conflicts. However, the most recent influx of refugees following the Taliban's return to power in 2021 has exacerbated the humanitarian challenges faced by neighboring countries like Iran and Pakistan. According to United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) estimates, over 6 million Afghans have been displaced by the ongoing conflict, with the majority seeking refuge in neighboring countries, including Iran and Pakistan (Moretti, 2021).

These refugees have faced immense hardships, from insufficient access to basic needs like healthcare, education, and employment, to facing the harsh conditions of living in overcrowded camps. As these crises unfold, humanitarian organizations, local governments, and international agencies have been forced to step up their efforts, yet the scale of the situation remains overwhelming. The influx of Afghan refugees is not only a humanitarian issue but also a geopolitical one, as it affects the foreign policy strategies of Iran and Pakistan.

Comparative Analysis of Iran and Pakistan's Reaction to Regional Challenges

Topic	Iran's Response	Pakistan's Response	Supporting Data
Humanitarian Emergency	Hosts ~3.75 million Afghan refugees, including undocumented migrants (UNHCR., 2024 a).	Deports 800,000+ Afghan refugees since 2023 (Council, 2024a).	Over 22.9 million Afghans require humanitarian aid (UNHCR, 2024); Pakistan hosts 1.75 million registered refugees(UNHCR., 2024).

Geopolitical Opportunity	Leverages refugee crisis to negotiate sanctions relief (Middle East Institute, 2025).	Strengthens ties with China via CPEC expansion(reuters, 2021).	Iran’s Chabahar Port counters CPEC; Pakistan secures \$60B in Chinese infrastructure projects (Shah, 2022).
Regional Diplomacy Role	Accused of using proxies to destabilize neighbors (Council., 2024a).	Retaliated against Iranian airstrikes in 2024(Pakistan., 2024).	Iran’s 2024 missile strikes led to civilian casualties (Council, 2024b).
Strategic Utilization of Refugee Crisis	Frames refugee management as part of security policy (Institute., 2025).	Links deportations to Taliban peace negotiations (Shah, 2022).	Pakistan’s deportation targets align with IMF negotiations (ORF., 2025).
Diplomatic Relations with the West	Resists U.S. pressure but seeks European aid(Koser K. , 2016).	Maintains U.S. security ties despite criticism (Atlantic Council, 2024a).	U.S. aid to Afghanistan dropped from 109B(2001-2021)to21B post-2021 (ORF, 2025).

The current Afghan refugee crisis has highlighted the convergence of humanitarian interests and geopolitical agendas, most notably for regional powers such as Iran and Pakistan. Both countries have discovered the refugee flow to be more than a humanitarian matter; it has become a principal bargaining chip in their foreign policy with influential international and regional players. The existence of millions of Afghan refugees has not only imposed great strains on the social systems and economies of these states but also opened up possibilities for exerting influence in international and regional diplomacy through their position as central players in the crisis.

Shah and Alizadeh in 2022 stated that, in Iran, the refugee crisis has emerged as a strategic tool in reinforcing its position in regional and global spheres. Having a long border with Afghanistan, Iran has been the frontline state in dealing with the refugee stream. The crisis has offered Iran the opportunity to bring its role as a frontier state in coping with regional uncertainty into international focus, especially as the wider Middle East and Central Asia are beset with major problems. Iran's engagement with Afghan refugees has allowed it to be an appealing recipient of aid from global organizations like the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR), as well as winning aid from global power. Iran has sought, in this manner, to acquire negotiating power for foreign policy, particularly in regards to its strained relations with Western powers, including the United States. Moreover Iran has articulated its refugee control as a

part of its more general regional security policy in the struggle against the Western chains (Patel N. A., 2019). For this reason, Iran's diplomatic approach has used the refugee crisis to not just win economic and humanitarian aid, but also how important it is in regional and worldwide geopolitics.

On the same lines, Pakistan’s response to the Afghan refugee crisis shows its geopolitical interests. Pakistan has been hosting Afghan refugees for years, but the magnitude of the recent influx created both a threat and an opportunity. The crisis has provided Pakistan with a way to position itself as a primary actor in South Asian geopolitics, especially with the United States and India. While Pakistan's allyship of the Taliban has complicated its relation with India, specifically in regards to the conflict of Kashmir, its position regarding dealing with Afghan refugees has also given it strength in its foreign diplomacy with international powers as well as regional ones (Yawar, 2025). Pakistan has utilized being a host nation to influence negotiations on peace talks with the Taliban as well as agree on political and security terms from global actors like China (Javaid F. &., 2016). The China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) has also further deepened the strategic relationship between the two countries, with Pakistan using the refugee card as a bargaining chip to obtain more diplomatic and economic support from China (Ali, 2025). This enables Pakistan to solidify its position not just in South Asia but globally as well (Secretariat., n.d).

The responses of Iran and Pakistan to the Afghan refugee crisis as a whole illustrate an overall pattern

in which humanitarian interest and geopolitical concerns are interlinked. Refugees have now created a space for state convergence: what their humanitarian need is continues to depend on the political and strategic interests of states. Having previously proved to be regional powers, Iran and Pakistan have shown how humanitarian crises can become a place for getting rich with the means of international relations, stressing their place in international geopolitics and promoting strategic policy (Diplomat., 2017).

Effect on Foreign Policy and Regional Stability

As Iran and Pakistan are both undergoing unprecedented redefinition of foreign policy, and having the Afghan refugee crisis of unprecedented rise, the two major regional players involved in the crisis have had the present opportunity to change the face of Iran and Pakistan. Afghan refugees have come in a sudden wave, and thus, the two states have to adopt their foreign policies to deal with new threats and yet to protect geopolitical interests. Most notably they both have taken stock of their role in regional politics and have, in counselling, scaled down (or up) their foreign policy to fit in with regional realities and the new international realities.

The crisis of refugees has been both challenge and opportunity for Iran. It seems that Iran's foreign policy after the 2021 period tries to work by cooperation at the regional level and multilateral diplomacy. Iran, too has historically been rather resistant to being associated with more far reaching international agendas and has maintained a tense relationship with the West and with the USA in particular. The dimensions of the refugee crisis now make Iran change its position on diplomatic isolation, to become more active in playing a role in controlling its neighboring countries and international agencies like the UN High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) and others regional organisations. Iran's entry to the regional security talks are also partly strategic in projecting the country's regional leadership and in avoiding the region destabilizing effects of the mass flow of refugees towards the countries in the region (Rahman, 2025). On one hand, through linking the

issue with Afghan refugees with the regional security talks Iran has brought the Afghan refugee crisis as a humanitarian issue, and on the other hand, as a strategic issue. Inserting humanitarian concerns into State's national security agendas, particular in conflict prone areas (Middle East and Central Asia) is one of the broader growing trends as it is stated (Khan S. U., 2025).

Iran's policy on the Afghan refugee crisis is also due to the need of Iran to maintain the regional stability over the desolate geopolitical situation as the case of the conflict with the United States and rivalry with Saudi Arabia. The refugee crisis, as a humanitarian crisis, has been of help to Iran in creating deeper diplomatic influence among other regional powers, and earning with the international community the right to everything that they have done.

Iran's projection of its leadership role in regional geopolitics and security through taking center stage in the Afghan refugee crisis, however, puts it in the cross hairs of a tricky balancing act between Western powers which continually reproach Iran on its human rights record, and aspiring regional powers like Russia and China from whom Iran desires the company if, as is happening, their own influence is on the rise (AmuzadehAraei S. T., 2025).

This reaction is also marked by the undertone of history of Pakistan's relations with Afghanistan rooted in common ethnic, cultural and historic affinities between the two countries. Never before has the influx of such a magnitude of refugees brought such unimaginable strain on its political and economic infrastructure for the Pakistani largesse to Afghan refugees. In addition, the refugee crisis divided Pakistan from India further, whose ties with Pakistan are already tense, due to the latter's suspected alliance with the Taliban regime. After Pakistan's alignment with the Taliban and considering the current Kashmir conflict, Pakistan's diplomatic relation with India has been complicated. In turn, this has created greater tensions, which India considers not only humanitarian, but as part of Pakistan's broader strategic connectivity with the Taliban and has wider strategic security influence implications (Bukhari, 2025).

Comparative Foreign Policy Responses to the Afghan Refugee Crisis: Iran vs. Pakistan

Foreign Policy Sector	Iran's Action	Pakistan's Action	Supporting Evidence
Regional Cooperation & Multilateral Diplomacy	High	Low	Iran takes the lead to address international organizations such as UNHCR (Ali, H. (2025)). Pakistan shuns multilateral agreements.
Strategic Use of Refugee Issue	High	High	Refugees are used by both countries for geopolitics negotiation (Edward Newman and Joanne van Selm, 2000)
Alignment with Russia & China	Medium	Low	Iran balances Russia/China and Western ties (Patel, 2019). Pakistan gives top priority to Chinese and U.S. relations.
Relations to the West	Medium	Low	Iran seeks alliances with regional states despite Western isolation (Ali, H. (2025)).
Regional Security Priority	High	Low	Iran prioritizes Middle Eastern/Central Asian security (Edward Newman and Joanne van Selm, 2000).
Regional Cooperation (with China)	Low	High	Pakistan intensifies China-RP relations via CPEC initiatives (Ali, H. (2025)).
Alignment with the Taliban	Low	High	Pakistan's support for the Taliban makes its relations with India more difficult (Cohen, 2013).
Tensions with India	Low	High	Refugee policies exacerbate Pakistan-India tensions in Kashmir (Cohen, 2013).
Balancing with the U.S.	Low	Medium	The two states share strained U.S. relations through Afghan policies (Ali, H. (2025)).
Managing Refugee Influx Internally	Low	Medium	Refugee burden triggers internal policy changes in the two states (Koser, 2018).

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Pakistan, for its part, has leveraged the position as host country of Afghan refugees to develop the geopolitical cooperation it shares with other global powers, particularly China. The deepening alignment between Pakistan and China has been hugely facilitated by mutual security and economic interests, where the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) represents a fundamental supporting pillar to their partnership. The refugee crisis has provided Pakistan with additional bargaining power in its relationship with China, attempting to gain more political and financial assistance for the management of the refugee population. Pakistan has, simultaneously, maintained its strategic relationship with the United States, aside from the complexities associated with the refugee crisis. The U.S. has been one of the most forceful backers of efforts by Pakistan to receive economic assistance and international backing, though the U.S. government itself has grumbled about Pakistani aid to the Taliban as well as about

doubt over the broader Afghan conflict (Mumtaz, 2025).

Pakistan's response to the crisis of refugees, thus, reflects the delicate balance that Pakistan has to achieve in its foreign policy. On the one hand, Pakistan wishes to project itself as a regional leader and deploy the concern over refugees to negotiate with China and the United States. Conversely, it has to contend with the domestic issue of the refugee influx, which strains its economic and social infrastructure. This is a broader phenomenon wherein local actors use humanitarian causes, such as refugee crises, to navigate the complex web of international relations and advance their strategic interests (Bukhari S. R., 2025).

The Multi-Polar World Order and Humanitarian Crises

The Afghan refugee crisis provides an important prism for analyzing the evolving landscapes of rising in the international system during times

multipolarity. Humanitarian crises in the present scenario become more common, and they undermine like classic power relations, which compel states to counter. These events not only press the humanitarian needs but also they do have large geopolitical consequences. The reaction in countries like Iran and Pakistan to the Afghan refugee crisis reveals how regional actors are exercising authority in global governance, security and, in particular, in human rights, and migration. The evolving roles of these caught in the crossfire: health care workers under attack countries, where humanitarian imperatives intersect with the strategic interests of regional and international powers and with the forces and factors that influence world relations at the present time. Concerning the management of such crises has traditionally been there, but in particular the humanitarian crises, those linked to refugees are also the dominant indices of fluctuating balance of the power in the world. Predominately by Western powers, mainly the United States and European Union, who applied political and military judgment by trying to affect international reactions (Munhazim, 2025). The emergence of new regional players in the region's geopolitical order begin to exploit key hosts for displaced populations to claim their place on the world stage, but there is an increasing involvement of countries like Iran and Pakistan to become influential embroiled in the shaping of the refugee in their countries (Nguyen, 2025). The situation of afghan refugee crises is been brought into broader trends in new civil society actors by the new media which influences the regional powers. These countries, which were disproportionate in their past relationship to the rest of the world, are no longer so, they are part and parcel of this expanding global power diffusion. Their reactions to the refugee crisis are on the margins of world diplomacy, are increasingly becoming central attention and element of the regional stability and international security. The strategic maneuver in the larger geopolitical chess game reflects their efforts to influence regional dynamics and secure economic and diplomatic gains. The increasing salience of regional players such as Iran and Pakistan is indicative of an overarching transition towards a multi-polar world order where numerous powers, state and non-state actors are

driving the international agenda. This new world order is marked by the decline hegemony of Western powers dating back to the classical imperial balance of 1815. Enable the traditional Western powers, which for a full century have been able to set international agenda dominated by Europe, and the United States. The world order is shifting and the new states have their own blocks to balance the relations. The power dynamics are changing which are allowing the smaller states to challenge the west-led status quo (Amir, 2025). The refugee misery in Afghanistan, so, is not only a humanitarian matter but symptom of shifting geopolitical order, in which the regional players are gaining but more critical for the global diplomacy's direction. Yet both Iran and Pakistan have tried to present their handling of the Afghan refugee crisis as part of a demonstration of their humanitarian duties, and their strategic interests in so doing elite using the question to progressive cause of their own. For instance in Iran, the government has employed its influence as a dominant force in troop-hosting country for Afghan refugees, to leverage for international assistance and to shore up its relationships with China and Russia - regional rivals even as it says it is a source of stability in the Middle East (Mohammad Toufeeq Shalizi, 2024). In the same way, Pakistan employed the Taliban and its role in sheltering Afghan refugees to obtain strategic gains, as part of a plan to spare them from economic woes due to the US sanctions and, to balance its relations with China and US (Qaderi, 2025). This dual role of these countries for humanitarian actors highlights geopolitical strategists and its complexity within larger geopolitical objectives in international relations, where humanitarian crises are typically embedded. As humanitarian considerations assume a growing prominence in the global political agenda, regional players such as Iran and Pakistan are changing the nature of managing the international crises towards a more multipolar world order. That shift is a part of a larger movement toward hegemony of the traditional Western centres which is being contested by the rise of non- Western nations. These regional actors are increasingly taking the helm in designing the future relations they want to see proving to be major, like migration, human rights, and security challenges. This transformative shift in no way undermines to be

the hub of diplomatic activity (Iqbal, 2025). This do challenges the norms of global governance but also signals the new trends of power flow, which emerges as the New Power Politics. Where, regional powers are assume to play an increased significant part in shaping the global structure. Under an increasingly multipolar world, the calculus of humanitarian crises in particular has even a more role in shaping the landscape. The Afghan refugee crisis is a vivid demonstration of how catastrophes are now part of the landscape of the diplomacy and global governance to grow feature of shaping the external relations of regional and global actors. In the emerging geopolitical situations and, world order, control of refugees' population becomes part of the

diplomatic strategy for required control which Iran and Pakistan are leading the change.

Lesson from Pakistan and Iran's reaction to Afghan refugees

The table below contains some of the most important insights drawn from the responses taken out the varying approaches the both countries confronted similar set of issues, and social factors due to geopolitical, economic, refugee crisis and pointing though pursued contrasting plans to tackle that provides useful perspectives on how refugee emergencies can influence the humanitarian point of departure, domestic policy and foreign affairs.

Key Themes	Pakistan's Response	Iran's Response
Regional Cooperation (UNHCR., 2023)	Worked together with UNHCR to receive 1.4 million registered Afghan refugees (2023).	Worked with UNHCR and IOM to assist 780,000 registered Afghan refugees (2023).
Humanitarian Assistance (UNHCR.b, 2023)	Supplied temporary shelter, meals, and polio inoculations through the Sehat Card scheme	Incorporated refugees into the country's health and subsidized fuel/utilities.
Geopolitical Ramifications (Smith, 2022)	Refugee flow strained relations with Afghanistan; used aid to leverage U.S./China relations.	Used refugee aid to offset Western sanctions and enhance relations with Syria/Iraq.
National Security	Blamed refugee camps for TTP recruitment; conducted military ops (e.g., Zarb-e-Azb) (Saeed, 2025).	Linked refugee management to countering ISIS-Khorasan; restricted border movements (Beckmann, 2014).
Economic Strain (Bank., 2022)	Host regions (KP/Balochistan) saw 22% rise in poverty (World Bank, 2022).	Employed refugees in construction/agriculture but faced 30% wage suppression.
Long-Term Integration (UNESCO., 2023)	Only 4% of Afghan refugees enrolled in schools (2023); limited vocational training.	Enrolled 48% of Afghan children in schools; offered Persian language programs.
Humanitarian Diplomacy (Elkahlout, 2024)	Secured \$500M in UN aid (2020-2023) but faced public backlash over resource strain.	Framed aid as "Islamic solidarity"; gained regional influence via OIC platforms.

In case of regional cooperation, both Pakistan and Iran cooperated with beyond the region powers or worked together administratively. Though the organizations such as the UNHCR for help and support. Pakistan's cooperation, though, generally has been reactive, focused on addressing short-term human needs like shelter, food and health care. Pakistan has its own, and complicated relationship with India, and a web of matters of security on its

borders that affects its response. By contrast, Iran's approach has been to include short term relief with structural pharmakonimic (health-knowledge-politic measures) by granting refugees health and education care. Iran has framed its humanitarian action in the broader context of a regional security policy, positioning itself as a stabilizing force in the Middle East. Both countries show the importance of international collaboration but Iran has calculated

to win the hearts of the people by portraying its humanitarian assistance as integral to its regional security interest while Pakistan's cooperation has revolved around the fulfillment of immediate specifications and not beyond, in providing relief aid. Both countries have also prioritized humanitarian assistance and relief; however both focus on short-term relief. Pakistan, however, was stretched to the limit to sustain these efforts, due to the sheer volume of refugees swamping its resources. Iran also invested not only in short-term relief, but also in long-term refugee support systems. Iran's approach was not limited to meeting immediate needs, but also included long-term care for the refugees, integrating them into the health and education systems. The comparison shows that the two countries knew it was necessary to react to short-term humanitarian needs but Iran's approach also reflects the importance of long-term assistance of the institutions of refugee integration and stability. The influence of the geopolitics on the foreign policy of the both states is enormous. For Pakistan, tensions with India, while dealing refugees influx could balance its relationship notably with the global players like United States and China. The tight rope walk influenced Pakistan's foreign policy, faced the double challenge of addressing refugees and regional security issues. For Iran, in contrast, the refugee crisis opened a new sphere of influence. By taking refugee assistance, Iran strengthened its posture in the Middle East and posed a more strategic hanging regional security and refugees of this broader that is part of this broader geopolitical setting and stability. Both countries show that humanitarian crises have very real, direct and far reaching impacts on foreign policy, but Iran have done a significantly better job of capitalizing on the refugee crisis to enhance its strategic position and Pakistan's response has been reactive because of its regional security situation. Both countries had national security needs. Pakistan was worried about security threats, such as the emergence of extremism in areas with high numbers of refugees. This concerned to response towards navigating the refugee population and close down the border. Iran, on the other hand, framed its refugee reaction within the broader package of regional security and for maintaining stability and challenges the prevention of the spread of

extremism. By controlling the refugees in a way that served its national security interests, Iran tried to mitigate the possible threats. Both countries had national security problems to address, but Iran's approach of refugees that can cohere to the region vs. Pakistan's focus to manage the security dangers is a variance from refugee camps. There were similar social and economic tensions in Pakistan and Iran as a consequence of the migrant flow. Pakistan was more impoverished among the areas with the refugees, which strain on the country's already scant resources. But Iran hit back with the economic burdens by integrating the refugees into the workforce, particularly in the form of agriculture and construction. In this way, Iran used was able in part to neutralize the economic issue, accessing refugee workforce and workforce and generating employment for Afghan refugees. Pakistan struggled most with the economic strain of overwhelming numbers of refugees and inferior economic strength, and while Iran capitalized on the refugee population economically, indicating a willingness toward a more practical point of view of economic integration. Iran's policy has been more forceful on long-term integration and schooling. Iran attempted to integrate Afghan children in its schools, and then refugees were guaranteed access to school and means for social integration. Refugees struggled less than other students to get into schools in Pakistan. There was limited access to education and job opportunities by refugees in Pakistan that exacerbated the issue in their long-term integration and policies of more integration the existence were mandatory. It compares Iran's relatively pro-active integration policies, particularly in the field of education, with Pakistan's failure to integrate refugees. This differential, in fact, calls for long term refugee integration planning in host countries. Finally, humanitarian diplomacy was exercised by both countries in order to garner international backing. Pakistan's diplomacy, enlisted with international help aligning with the domestic political requirement of facing up to the refugee influx. This tended to lead to a reactive approach of confronting the refugee crisis. Iran used its humanitarian diplomacy as a tool to increase its regional influence and strengthen relations with regional countries as well as to show itself as a

regional leader in refugee assistance. Iran was able to exploit the crisis, due to its humanitarian diplomacy approach, and to strengthen its diplomatic grip on the gulf. They both have used humanitarian diplomacy to gain international support, but Iran has done better applying it to expand its influence and stability quietly in the region.

Conclusion

The struggle of Afghan refugees in Pakistan and Iran testifies to the possibility of wars to create. It cannot only humanitarian disasters to be motors of change in international relations. It not only reiterated the urgency of immediate international collaboration and humanitarian aid, yet it has also emphasized the geopolitical significance of such crises in a multi-polar world. While Pakistan and Iran both contend with what repatriation advocate organizations call 'displacement by design' that from refugees on the move, the responses of these results states are indicative of broader trends in international relations where humanitarian imperatives increasingly shape foreign policy and diplomacy. Pakistan and Iran responded differently to the Afghan refugee problem. Whereas, Iran's response was a more active one with long term engagement and strategic humanitarian diplomacy interests in view, Pakistan's was more security interest based and colored combined with regional security by its fragile dynamics with India. The Iranian response was more active, a combination of prolonged engagement and strategic humanitarian diplomacy related to regional security concerns - whereas the Pakistani response was more security interest-based and based on its fragile relationship with India. Both of those reactions address the difficulties of responding to refugee crises, and the needs of host and long-countries in providing temporary humanitarian aid term integration policy. The degree and its lack of cooperation between the states regarding these issues is a result that has transnational repercussions, and which longer-term transformation of world affairs, with reference to the international governance and diplomacy, in times of power transition. To sum it up, the Afghan refugee problem has affected both the foreign policies of Iran and Pakistan. For Iran, it has forced a strategic review of its foreign policy toward greater regional co-operation and multilateral

diplomacy. This has been a difficult balancing act for Pakistan as well, as it has ratcheted up Tension with India while trying to work out how it should remain on good terms with other major international actors including China and the United States. Subjecting Humanitarian Responses to Geopolitical Agendas In both circumstances the responses of two nations, one an atomic power and the other a regional oil resource power, illustrate the impact of when humanitarian embedded with the geopolitical interests, and crises become whose decisions impact foreign policy choices and regional stability. These reactions illustrate the growing complexity of world affairs in the 21st century, where geopolitical and humanitarian stakes are more intertwined. Second, their presence in these countries solidifies the intersectionalism of geopolitics and also offers a rare glimpse of humanitarian catastrophe and the game-logic of international relations in an ascending multi-polar world. While Iran and Pakistan have been issue, their responses have served as grappling with the test cases of regional diplomacy and cooperation terms where emergency constitute significant source of foreign policy and global linkages. The Afghani refugee crisis is a clear example of how such crises can push states to re-evaluate their stance and to jointly act more energetically to address global challenges- thus illustrating the relevance of humanitarian diplomacy towards a more multipolar world.

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